

Mobile interactive storytelling at the Ancient Agora of Athens: exploring the right balance between the site and the digital application

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Abstract

Historical sites are places where the past and the present, the tangible and the intangible meet and offer visitors an opportunity to immerse themselves in history. The design of digital mobile applications for open-air archaeological sites presents specific challenges; however, it also has the potential to enhance visitor experience in unique ways. In this paper, we focus on the design and evaluation of a dramatized multimedia interactive story for the Ancient Agora (market) of Athens, with the objective to bring the site's function and essence to life. The iterative design and evaluation approach we have followed revealed elements concerning the effective balance between the characteristics of the site, the needs of the visitor and the possibilities offered by the technology, including the role and use of 3D and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies, the importance of sound and the level of interaction desired by the users.

1 Introduction

Digital multimedia mobile applications for cultural heritage are found nowadays in museums and cultural sites worldwide and are credited for ensuring access to information, and catering to differing visitor styles, interests and needs [Mcgo12]. Digital storytelling in cultural heritage contexts has been universally recognized as a direction that cultural heritage institutions, including museums and historical sites, need to invest in to attract and engage their audiences [Twis08]. The CHESS project [Rous18] explored different aspects of digital personalized

storytelling and its successor, EMOTIVE (Emotive virtual cultural experiences through personalized storytelling), has been working towards the identification of a conceptual framework [Perr17] for the use of emotions in digital storytelling for heritage.

Historical sites, as places where the tangible and intangible meet, serve as living evidence of the sociopolitical and administrative functions of their era [Dami08]. The experience takes place at the actual site where history happened, thus contributing towards enhancing the visitors' immersion. While engagement in a museum tends to be predominantly a visual affair, in an outdoor setting multiple senses are stimulated with the potential to place the visitor in direct connection with heritage, enabling engagement at an emotional, affective level rather than at a purely informational one [Petr16].

Studies, including our previous work in the Ancient Agora [Rous17], indicate that using mobile devices to support the visit in a cultural site, either indoor or outdoor, comes with a number of complex challenges that need to be addressed during design and/or deployment. These may include the design of the multimedia content delivery, balancing visitors' attention between the environment and the device, navigation, usability, social aspects, and personalization [Rous18]. Outdoor settings can be really challenging also from a technical point of view, due to the possible lack of effective internet connectivity and issues such as intense sunlight that can also impede the presentation of visual material on screen.

In this paper, we present the design and development of an interactive digital storytelling experience for mobile devices for the archaeological site of the Ancient Agora (market) of Athens, with the objective to explore the opportunities and challenges of mobile-mediated, digital storytelling in an outdoor setting. In Section 2, we discuss the story concept and objectives and how these inform the design and technical specifications of the digital experience. Section 3 presents the evaluation of the prototype experience and Section 4 draws together results and insights. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Designing a digital interactive storytelling app for the Ancient Agora

The first step for the design of the experience was to clearly define its objectives in collaboration with the site's experts. The aim of the experience is to promote:

- emotional engagement and empathy of the visitor with the site and chosen historical period,
- a sense of the structure and complexity of the archaeological site and of the athenian society,

- reflection and perspective-taking about the people of the chosen historical period.

In this section we present the site's characteristics and how they informed design decisions about the concept and implementation of the storytelling experience, in relation to the aforementioned objectives. In each paragraph we discuss the interaction between the experience objectives and site needs, identifying concrete requirements and design decisions for the resulting experience (R1 – R11).

2.1 The site

The Ancient Agora of Athens is located in the northwest of the Acropolis. The Agora's initial use was that of a commercial and residential gathering place. The archaeological site is comprised of the outdoor site and a museum and it features multiple buildings from different eras, including 14 important monuments from the Classical period. The visitor wandering around the preserved outdoor site can mostly see only the foundations of these buildings and the well preserved Temple of Hephaestus. The site is large, covering an area of roughly 20 acres. The site size and state of preservation implies the following two requirements:

- **R1 - Guided navigation.** The state of preservation of the monuments does not support visitor navigation by identifying concrete landmarks in space. GPS or another type of geo-localization technique is needed to support navigation from one point of interest to the other.
- **R2 – Circular visitor path.** The site is large and the walking distance between points of interest does not favor a free exploration experience. In this case, we designed the storytelling to be experienced at specific points of interest. These points are selected to be relatively close and consecutive in space, so as to minimize walking distance for the visitor in the large archaeological site, and to return with the visitor to the point where the experience started. When concluding the story part at a specific point and according to her choices, the user is guided towards the next point of interest.

The Agora was the center of Ancient Athens and most of its administrative and trading functions were located at this site, a place where notable historical figures, such as Pericles or Socrates, lived and orated. Hence, it is a place of the highest historical significance, visited by millions of tourists throughout the year. However, as is the case with most open-air archaeological sites, to the non experts, the value of what today remains of the site cannot be immediately perceived without a guide. This leads to the following requirement:

- **R3 – Visual reconstruction.** The state of preservation of the Agora monuments and buildings introduces the need for appropriate augmentations and reconstructions presented to the user, to better understand the features of the site.

2.2 Historical setting and period

Mainly focused around the trade and economical function of the Agora, the setting of the experience highlights this attractive aspect, rich in images and sounds – the crowded market with the traders benches not dissimilar to the markets and bazaars of the East, side by side with temples, altars and emblematic buildings of the classical antiquity.

- **R4 – Audio reconstruction.** Re-creating the sense of being in the market cannot be accomplished solely through visual augmentation (R3), but first and foremost with audio augmentations. Sound is key to reproduce the rich soundscape one would experience being present in the market in Ancient Athens.

The historical context of our story is the Ancient Agora of Athens during the classical period (480-323 BCE). The story unfolds at the beginning of the 4th century, one of the worst periods in the history of the city. Athens has been defeated in the recent Peloponnesian War and faces a deep crisis. During this period the life status of many Athenians is shattered. People of previous affluence are ruined and now forced to manual labour to survive. In a society where manual labor is a major socio-economical differentiating factor and is in a sense frowned upon, these changes have had a significant impact. The financial aspects of the market become the incentive for deeper reflection on issues very much relevant also today: the financial crisis and its implications, ethical, political and social, issues of distribution of wealth, and more personal issues of coping in times of crisis.

- **R5 – Digital storytelling.** Using digital storytelling as a tool to convey the historical context through the perspective of personal stories of inhabitants of that time.

2.3 Interactive storytelling as the experience type

Interactive storytelling, is defined as a branching narrative where the user can directly influence the story plot and the characters' decisions, and in this way, create different story lines and alternative endings. This experience type is in fact a specialization of the wider concept of digital storytelling where the user is presented with narratives and stories related to the site; options, when available, allow the user to choose between different stories or to select additional informational content.

- **R6 – Interactive digital storytelling.** A key design choice for the experience was to employ interactive storytelling as the experience type.

Interaction and choices at the story plot level is the defining characteristic for the interactive storytelling literature genre. This approach is common in the Interactive Fiction literature domain, and in gaming settings. However, this approach very rarely has been applied in the heritage domain, especially for on-site visits.

Why interactive storytelling?

Our initial approach for mobile digital storytelling in museums, in the context of the CHES project and later, employed storytelling techniques where the user was guided around the galleries in a story-centric way. Characters of the past spoke to the user through the device, in some cases simply reminiscing personal stories, in others cases inviting the user to play a role and “help” them complete specific tasks. This approach aimed to engage the user through the illusion of being part of the story in some way and having direct interaction with the main character. As discussed in [Rous18] and [Kati18], although these experiences featured several branching and decisions points, were consistently characterized by several users as “too guided” and “too linear”, more so by those with experience in computer games. Users often referred to a “lack of interaction”, which, when probing further, was in fact rooted in a sense of lack of actual control over the story plot. The mobile device and perceived nature of the storytelling experience, as a mobile app, created the preconception that the story would be “interactive”. Moreover, this kind of interaction that offered only informational content selection and had no true effect over the story plot left the visitor with this sense of lack of control.

To address this finding we turned naturally to techniques established by interactive storytelling and its concrete premise that “story richness depends on the functional significance of each choice and the perceived completeness of choices offered” [Craw05].

- **R7 - Interactive storytelling with meaningful decision points.** Our interactive storytelling experience features 7 decision points at each story path and 9 alternate endings defined by combinations of these decision points. To address the issue of “functional significance” of the choices, some of the decision point, as it becomes evident, are later on decisive about how the story unfolds, whereas others are of an ethical or emotional nature. One of the paths, depending on the users’ choices, leads to an “anticlimax” ending, similarly to what sometimes happens also in real life.

2.4 The story concept

The main character of the story is Hermias, a slave. Slavery in ancient Athens is a controversial institution in the “cradle of Democracy” as ancient Athens has been characterized throughout the ages. This interesting interaction between the political state of Athens and the established institution of slavery is by itself an incentive for reflection on the period.

What is the “truth“ of the slave in ancient Athens and how can this be leveraged with the pre-conceptions of the audience? The divide between free citizens and slaves seems to be a simplistic view of this society. Things were more complex, with slaves becoming rich bankers, (as is the case with the main character of our story), citizens being accused of being descendants of slaves, etc. There are gaps in our knowledge and these offer an opportunity for interesting historical fiction.

- ***R8 – An Athenian slave as the main character.*** A slave, Hermias, has been chosen as the main character of the story, with the objective to promote the emotional engagement of the visitor. Hermias experiences concerns and feelings that are valid and timely also today, including financial insecurity, personal fear for the future of the individual and their family and loved ones, feelings of trust, or lack of, towards the others, etc.

2.5 The story plot

The story starts one early morning in 398 BCE by following around the main character, Hermias the slave, as he prepares to go to the market. He is wondering whether he should wear his amulet, which features the head of God Hermes, or leave it at home. Hermias was named after this amulet, with which he was found abandoned as a baby. This is the first decision the user is asked to make for Hermias: to wear the amulet or not? The user is addressed in first person when asked to make choices (Table 1).

The visitor then "follows" Hermias as he walks around the market, where he first meets his master Nicocles and then continues on to run errands. In the course of these interactions and according, again, to the user's choices, he speaks with different merchants and acquaintances, answering or not to their, sometimes, personal questions, about his origins. If the user, at the outset, chose that Hermias should wear his amulet while at the market, then the experience will include merchants asking Hermias about his amulet; otherwise it will not. While at the market, Hermias hears news of a cargo ship sinking and realizes that his master Nicocles had invested heavily in this ship as a last attempt to recover financially. The story continues with Hermias in

emotional distress about how to handle these news and with deep concern about how his master's financial disaster would affect him. The user then follows Hermias' exchanges with different characters in the story and is given the choice to affect his decisions and behavior. These choices define the ending of the story, which is also directly relevant to Hermias' initial choice to wear his amulet or not.

Nicocles is planning to ask Eucrates, a ruthless merchant of shields who accumulated his wealth during the war, for a loan. Eucrates is willing to give Nicocles the loan, but in exchange he asks for the ownership of Hermias. Eucrates' proposal came out of the blue. You...

- are aware of your status and do not react...
- forget your status and react with insolence...

Table 1: Example of a decision point.

2.6 The storytelling app

To create and deliver the aforementioned experience, we used the *Narralive* authoring and experiencing tools, also employed within the EMOTIVE project [Kati19a]. Specifically, the experiences were created through the use of the Storyboard Editor, a web-based authoring tool for interactive digital storytelling which produces a mobile app for devices based on Android v4.1 (API 16) and later. More details about the app can be found in [Kati19b].

The story is divided into chapters related with the location and function of different buildings. The users are guided by the app to go to each of the points of interest and then access the relevant part of the experience. At certain points, visitors can have the possibility to access on-demand supplementary information about each specific point of interest (Fig. 1).

The story is implemented as a multimedia experience. Our previous work in the Agora [Rous17] and other sites [Rous18] clearly indicated that extensive use of visuals absorbs the users attention on the screen and away from their surroundings. In this experience we opted for a predominantly audio based experience, with minimum visuals on screen. Initial formative design session led to the following design decisions for the prototype presented in this work:

- **R9 – Audio based experience.** The experience unfolds through audio segments, alternating a narrator with conversations between the story characters.
- **R10 – Supporting use of visuals.** Images are used sparingly, to (a) support navigation through maps and (b) show specific buildings or objects that are not currently identifiable on site (like the “Tholos” building, as reconstructions).

- **R11 – Use of VR and AR.** Tests on site as well as previous experience with mobile device mediated AR and VR outdoors revealed that issues such as sun glare and screen size can significantly diminish the added value of the use of these technologies. This issue is further discussed in Section 5.

Fig. 1: Selected screenshots depicted aspects of the story in the mobile app.

The next sections discuss the expert evaluation and its results for the prototype experience.

3 Expert Evaluation

After several iterations working with design ideas and prototypes on site, a first complete demo version of the experience was evaluated in November 2018 by 15 invited visitors from around the world who were selected according to their experience as domain experts, interpreters, and designers of similar experiences (e.g. archaeologists, museologists, experience designers and historians). These invited participants were asked to view the experience from the perspective of a visitor to the Agora, but also as experts, taking into account their experience on what works and what doesn't for visitors in similar contexts (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Users experiencing the interactive storytelling app

The participants were given the mobile device and were asked to follow the experience while being discreetly observed by the evaluators. Eight (8) of the participants experienced the story in pairs, using one device and headphone splitters. The reason for this was that we wished to examine the conversation between these pairs of users as they explored the site together.

4 Results and discussion

In this section we discuss selected findings from the evaluation of the storytelling prototype.

4.1 Establishing emotional connection

The users agreed that the story was engaging and they felt immersed when having to make decisions; those in pairs discussed with their companions how to proceed and why at each decision point. As some users commented, the experience helped them “imagine different aspects of life and social interaction in Athens”.

An important comment, however, related to the believability of the character of the slave. In particular, it was suggested that those with no pre-existing knowledge of the role and status of slaves in the athenian society, and with specific preconceptions about slavery, felt that the character of the slave was not realistic, neither in attitude nor in the exchanges with his master. This lack of context and subsequent lack of believability about the character was decisive in breaking the engagement and immersion in the story.

Secondly, as also discussed in [Kati18], interactive storytelling as an experience type in heritage also needs to take into consideration personalization in terms of the genre that the story belongs to. It is to be expected that this type of social drama may not be interesting or appealing as a

genre for specific users, and indeed, there were those who found the story “only mildly interesting” or even “boring”.

4.2 Understanding the historical context

One of the reported positive aspects of the experience was the fact that it helped the users “get a sense of what it was like to live in the past”. However, as already discussed, the lack of historical contextualization about slavery at the beginning of the story seemed to affect emotional engagement. And, on the other hand, as some users commented, the availability of information in menus within the story flow was also considered confusing, or responsible for breaking immersion and engagement.

The challenge of the right balance between engaging storytelling and information delivery remains a strong one and in need of further exploration to identify the optimal techniques to combine both.

In relation to the site itself, again an interesting challenge emerged from the evaluation: on the one hand, some users reported that even though the visuals on-screen had been kept to a minimum, again their attention was frequently drawn to the device, hindering them from connecting with the physical site. They proposed pauses to the experience or prompts to look around in order to enhance their engagement with the surrounding physical world. However, at the same time they felt that the state of preservation of the site would benefit from a richer multimedia experience at points. We are investigating the application of 3D soundscapes to enhance the visitor experience, as well as applications of VR or AR, which could be meaningful and effective taking into account the device size and sun glare.

4.3 Cultivating reflection and perspective taking

Taking into account the conversation that sparked between visitors during and after the experience, we observed that, in some cases, the experience was successful in promoting reflection and perspective-taking. Users had a chance to experience the past through the perspective of one of its inhabitants. In fact, their disbelief about the character’s status and behavior turned into a positive point as it triggered discussions about the role of slavery in the Athenian society, in comparison to other cultures and societies of that time but also later.

In the cases where the experience was shared between two visitors, perspective-taking and reflection seemed to be much more pronounced, attesting once again to the value of social interaction in heritage, as also discussed in [Perr19].

5 Conclusions and future work

In this work, we presented the design and evaluation of a prototype interactive storytelling experience for the Ancient Agora of Athens. The iterative design and evaluation approach we have followed revealed elements and limitations concerning the effective balance between the characteristics of the site, the needs of the visitor and the possibilities offered by the technology. Based on the preliminary findings of our evaluation, we propose ways to address these challenges. As we work towards a newer version of the digital experience, we are looking further into the role and use of 3D and augmented technologies for the site, the importance of sound, and the level of interaction desired by the users.

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